

NOTE ON OXIDATION OF FERROUS IRON WITH POTASSIUM IODATE.

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Fe⁺⁺ has been estimated potentiometrically against KIO₃ in presence of an excess of HCl and in an atmosphere of CO₂.

Ferrous iron has been determined potentiometrically by titrating it against standard potassium iodate in presence of an excess of hydrochloric acid in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide.

A known weight of ferrous ammonium sulphate was taken in the titration vessel, from which the air was swept off by a current of carbon dioxide and a required amount of hydrochloric acid was added to keep its concentration above 4*N*. Standard potassium iodate was then added from a burette, the mixture was stirred by a mechanical stirrer and the progress of oxidation followed with the potentiometer.

In these titrations, with the addition of standard potassium iodate the E. M. F. rose steadily till the equivalence-point. At the equivalence-point, there was a sharp jump in potentials in each case. For the addition of 0.05 c.c. of the titrant, the inflection potential was of the order of 220 millivolts. After the equivalence-point, there was again a rise in the potential which became steady on further addition of the reagent.

From the volume of the potassium iodate solution, required in each titration corresponding to the equivalence-point, the amount of the salt was calculated. The values obtained are compared with the amounts of the salt taken in the table given below.

TABLE I.

Ferrous ammonium sulphate.			
Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
0.7830 g.	0.7827 g.	0.3788 g.	0.3784 g.
0.6215	0.6211	0.2397	0.2395
0.5174	0.5172	0.1190	0.1187
		0.0580	0.0576

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